

Semiotic Analysis of Animated Advertising Pocari Sweat

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ABSTRACT

Animated advertising is a promotional media that uses animation to introduce its products. One product that uses animation as an advertising medium is Pocari Sweat. In October 2020, Pocari Sweat issued an advertisement using its anime animation techniques with the theme Pocari Sweat: Sweat For Dream. To be able to find out the meaning of verbal and non-verbal semiotic messages contained in the Pocari Sweat: Sweat for Dream advertisement. This research is qualitative research using Saussure's semiotic model approach to analyze objects through the stages of signs, markers and signs, while Herbert Blumer's symbolic interaction theory analyzes objects through verbal and non-verbal signs. The results of this research show that the message to be conveyed in this advertisement is an invitation to stay enthusiastic and not give up easily in achieving your dreams, which is packaged through verbal and non-verbal signs in this advertisement

INTRODUCTION

Advertising is the spearhead in marketing or selling products. Advertising is an art of persuasion, where advertising is used as a means of communication used by communicators, in this case companies or producers, to convey information about goods or services to the public, especially customers, through mass media. Advertisements are created with the aim of providing information and persuading consumers to try or follow what is in the advertisement, which can be in the form of activities to consume the products and services offered.

Through its development, producers and companies always try to make advertisements as attractive as possible, so that the message content of an advertisement can be conveyed well. One way of delivering advertisements that is currently a trend is presenting advertisements packaged using animation techniques. One company that uses animation techniques in making its advertisements is PT. Amerta Indah Otsuka, which is one of the companies that produces the famous isotonic drink, namely Pocari Sweat.

Pocari Sweat has released its newest advertisement, still using animation techniques and soft selling marketing techniques, which was published on October 2 2020 on the PocariID YouTube channel with the title Pocari Sweat "Sweat For Dream", which was done directly by a Japanese animation studio, namely StudioMaruyama Animation Produce Project Association (MAPPA). This Pocari Sweat advertisement is unique in its advertising packaging concept, by conveying a motivational narrative that provides encouragement and an invitation to teenagers to never give up and hesitate in achieving the dreams they have, and is supported by neat animated visuals so that it becomes an inspiration. This ad has a special appeal, compared to other similar animated adverts. Proven by the numbersviewers Pocari Sweat advertisement "Sweat For Dream" This, which was only published 1 month ago, has already reached 2.5 million viewers, while the Sasa product advertisement which uses similar animation techniques received 2 million viewers within 6 months of its publication.

Based on the background above, the problem formulation that will be researched is to examine how semiotic analysis in Pocari Sweat advertisements with the theme Sweat For Dream. And if we refer to the formulation of the problem, the aim to be achieved in this research is to find out the meaning of the verbal and non-verbal semiotic messages contained in the Pocari Sweat: Sweat For Dream advertisement.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Semiotics

The word semiotics comes from the Greek, semeion which means "sign" or seme which means "interpreter of signs". Semiotics has its roots in classical and scholastic studies of the arts of logic, rhetoric and poetics (Kurniawan, 2001:49). Semiotics as a model of social science understands the world as a system of relationships that has a basic unit called a "sign" (Sobur, 2009: 87).

This semiotic theory was put forward by Ferdinand De Saussure (1857-1913). In this theory, semiotics is divided into two parts, namely signifiers (signifier) and sign (signified). Signifiers are seen as physical forms or forms that can be recognized through the form of architectural works, while signs are seen as meanings that are revealed through the concepts, functions and values contained in architectural works.

According to Saussure, signs consist of: "Sounds and images, mentioned signifier or signifiers, and concepts from sounds and images, are mentioned signified". Saussure places signs in the context of human communication by sorting things out by doing what is called signifier (marker) and signified (sign). Signifier is a meaningful sound or meaningful scribble (material aspect), namely what is said or what is written and read. Signified is a mental image, namely a thought or concept of the mental aspect of language. Saussure described signs as consisting of signifier (marker) and signified (sign), as follows:

Image 1. Theory of Ferdinand De Saussure
(Source: Bambang & Emilsyah, 2013:77)

Saussure mentions a signifier as a sound or meaningful stroke, while the signified is a mental image or concept of something from the signifier. The relationship between the physical existence of signs and mental concepts is called signification. In other words, signification is an effort to give meaning to the world.

Symbolic Interaction Theory

The concept of symbolic interaction theory was introduced by Herbert Blumer around 1939. In the scope of sociology, this idea was actually put forward by George Herbert Mead, but was later modified by Blumer to achieve certain goals. This theory has good ideas, but is not as deep and specific as proposed by G.H. Mead.

Symbolic interactions are based on ideas about the individual and his interactions with society. The essence of symbolic interaction is an activity that is characteristic of humans, namely communication or exchange of symbols that are given meaning. This perspective suggests that human behavior should be seen as a process that allows humans to shape and regulate their behavior by taking into account the expectations of other people with whom they interact. It is the definitions they give to other people, situations, objects and even themselves that determine human behavior. In this context, meaning is constructed in the process of interaction and this process is not a neutral medium that allows social forces to play their role, but rather is the actual substance of social organization and social forces.

According to symbolic interaction theory, social life is basically human interaction that uses symbols. They are interested in how humans use symbols that represent what they mean to communicate with each other. And also the influence that the interpretation of these symbols has on the behavior of the parties seen in social interactions.

METHODOLOGY

In this research, the researcher used a type of descriptive qualitative research method where descriptive qualitative research aims to seek an in-depth understanding of a symptom, fact or reality. Facts, realities, problems, symptoms and events can only be understood if researchers explore them in depth and are not limited to surface views. This depth is what characterizes the qualitative method, as well as its superior factor. The definition of the qualitative research method itself is a research method used to research the conditions of natural objects, where the researcher is the key instrument, data collection techniques are carried out triangulation (combined), data analysis is inductive, and the results of qualitative research emphasize meaning and generalization. .

In this research, the object of research will be the semiotic meaning in the animated advertisement "Pocari Sweat: Sweat For Dream". And the subject of this research is the advertisement "Pocari Sweat: Sweat For Dream".

The data sources from this research are divided into 2, namely: primary data in the form of research or observations on the animated advertisement broadcast Pocari Sweat: Sweat For Dream which has a duration of 1 minute. For data sources, researchers got it from the YouTube site. And secondary data, namely library research, is the method used in research to collect data from literature related to the problem that will be discussed and then analyzed. This

literature is in the form of books, journals, internet sites related to the problems the author is researching.

Data collection techniques are techniques or methods used in research to collect data. In this research, the author used data collection techniques, namely: interviews, observation, and documentation/literature study.

The data analysis process begins by reviewing all available data, both primary data and secondary data. The data analysis process carried out in this research refers to the data analysis process presented by Miles and Huberman (in S. Arikunto, 2010: 44), namely after the data has been read, studied and analyzed, then the data is reduced, presented and conclusions are drawn and verify it.

RESULT

PT. Amerta Indah Otsuka

When it was first established in 1997, Otsuka was an affiliate company of Otsuka Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd. Japan which began its journey in Indonesia under the name PT. Otsuka Beautiful Ship. This company was formed from the results of a joint investment between Otsuka Pharmaceutical Japan and PT Kapal Api with Pocari Sweat as its first product. Then in 1999, PT Kapal Indah Otsuka changed its name to PT. Amerta Indah Otsuka.

PT Amerta Indah Otsuka has a company vision, namely, to become a brilliant company, by making a significant and trusted contribution to consumers and society. And the mission of the PT Amerta Indah Otsuka company is to develop and retain high quality employees to produce high quality products, make the needs and welfare of consumers and society the main priority, capture opportunities in all aspects appropriately and innovatively for consumer welfare and satisfaction and development. company, develop and maintain mutually beneficial relationships with business partners, become a trusted company (Diah Ayu Budiarti, 2018:75).

Pocari Sweat

Pocari Sweat is an isotonic drink to replace lost body fluids. Pocari Sweat is made based on scientific research so that its composition is measurable and similar to body fluids. Pocari Sweat can quickly absorb into the body because of its good osmolarity and consists of electrolytes to help replace body fluids. Pocari Sweat does not contain preservatives, artificial sweeteners, soda or caffeine, so it is safe for consumption. The composition of Pocari Sweat consists of sugar, glucose, citric acid, sodium chloride, vitamin C, potassium chloride, calcium lactate, magnesium, carbonate and citrus flavor (aio.co.id, 2020).

Pocari Sweat Advertisement : Sweat for Dream

Pocari Sweat : Sweat For Dream is a commercial advertisement from the well-known isotonic drink product company, namely Pocari Sweat. Which was published on October 2 2020 on the PocariID YouTube channel with the title Pocari Sweat "Sweat For Dream". This 60 second advertisement was done directly

by an animation studio from Japan, namely the Maruyama Animation Produce Project Association (MAPPA) studio. The purpose of this advertisement is not only to promote its products, but also to promote the annual talent search event held by Pocari Sweat with the theme SMA Stars, which was held in 2019. In 2020, Pocari Sweat will also hold the talent search event again, At the 2020 SMA Bintang event, Pocari Sweat raised the theme "Sweat For Dream" which means that if they are willing to sweat and try, they will be able to achieve it.

DISCUSSION

Analysis of the Meaningful Content of the Pocari Sweat Advertisement: Sweat For Dream Dissected Based on Signs, Omens, and Signifiers.

First Illustration

Visual

Figure 2. Illustration of a teenager sitting pensive
(Source: <https://youtu.be/c2JU7eP4I8k>)

Sign

Narrator: "When you chase your dreams, you may feel lonely."

Marker

A teenager and girl are sitting pensively alone, looking down with flat lips, and dark/dim background colors.

Sign

Both characters are feeling lonely and not enthusiastic

2nd Illustration

Visual

Figure 3. Illustration of Teenagers Practicing
(Source: <https://youtu.be/C2ju7ep4i8k>)

Sign

Narrator: "But don't give up, you are not alone. Move forward together step by step, enjoying a journey full of smiles and memories. Even though we are different, our spirit remains the same."

Marker

Several characters are shown doing exercises with their respective hobbies, with enthusiasm and sweat. And look at the earnest expression that can be seen from the raised eyebrows and wide-open eyes.

Sign

Even though they have different hobbies/abilities, they must not give up and must keep trying to achieve their dreams with enthusiasm.

3rd Illustration

Visual

Figure 4. Illustration of a Teenager Looking at the Sky
(Source: <https://youtu.be/C2ju7ep4i8k>)

Sign

Narrator: "Don't give up on your dreams because there will be friends with you, believe that tomorrow will be brighter."

Marker

The teenage character who was previously sitting pensively raised his face with a faint smile. And the nuances of the illustration, which were originally dim, changed to be brighter.

Sign

The return of enthusiasm and optimism to the character to achieve his dreams.

4rd Illustration Visual

Figure 5. Illustration of the Text Sweat for Dream
(Source: <https://youtu.be/C2ju7ep4i8k>)

Sign

Narrator: "Sweat For Dream".

Marker

The illustrations that form the text are displayed Sweat For dream, and the loud and enthusiastic intonation of the narrator who utters the sentences Sweat For Dream.

Sign

They are reminiscent of audience to stay enthusiastic and fight to achieve your dreams.

5rd Illustration Visual

Figure 6. Illustration of a Teenager Playing Drums Enthusiastically
(Source: <https://youtu.be/C2ju7ep4i8k>)

Sign

The music of the song Zenryoku Shounen with the dominant musical instrument, namely drums, which gives an impression energetic and a boisterous spirit.

Marker

Several characters are shown doing their respective hobbies with enthusiasm, which can be seen from their lively movements and the smiles that radiate from their faces. Coupled with music from Zenryoku Shounen which adds an enthusiastic feel to the video.

Sign

This illustration shows a sense of enthusiasm and desire to achieve a dream. And the song Zenryoku Shounen has the meaning that there will always be a way and hope to achieve your dreams. Which further strengthens the spirit not to give up easily in achieving your dreams.

6rd Illustration

Visual

Figure 7. Illustration of Several High School Teenagers Running Together
(Source: <https://youtu.be/C2ju7ep4i8k>)

Sign

The music of the song Zenryoku Shounen with the dominant musical instrument, namely drums, which gives an impression energetic and a boisterous spirit.

Marker

An illustration of several high school teenagers is shown running full of enthusiasm and hope, with smiling faces and eyes wide open.

Sign

This illustration indicates that the target of this advertising promotion is high school teenagers, and invites them to fight passionately and achieve their dreams together.

**7rd Illustration
Visual**

Figure 8. Illustration of a Teenager Drinking Pocari Sweat
(Source: [Https://Youtu.Be/C2ju7ep4i8k](https://youtu.be/C2ju7ep4i8k))

Sign

The music of the song Zenryoku Shounen with the dominant musical instrument, namely drums, which gives an impression energetic and a boisterous spirit.

Marker

Illustration of a teenager drinking Pocari Sweat while dripping with sweat.

Sign

This illustration indicates that it reminds the audience to always drink Pocari Sweat so that they can restore lost body fluids after activities.

**8rd Illustration
Visual**

Figure 9. Illustration Go Sweat Go Ion
(Source: [Https://Youtu.Be/C2ju7ep4i8k](https://youtu.be/C2ju7ep4i8k))

Sign

Narrator: "Go Sweat Go Ion".

Marker

The slogan text appears Go Sweat Go Ion, and an illustration of 2 teenagers who are full of enthusiasm and sweat, with smiles on their faces.

Sign

The slogan and illustration indicate that we should not be afraid to sweat, we must adopt good habits to stay active and do activities that can have a good impact on ourselves.

Analysis Based on Symbolic Interaction

Verbal

Verbal messages (Suranto, 2010:127) use words that show various aspects of reality that exist within a person. Words as expressions are packaged in two ways, namely vocally or verbally and non-vocally or written.

The Pocari Sweat: Sweat For Dream advertisement is formed by spoken verbal messages delivered by several male and female narrators which are spoken alternately and continuously. More clearly, the verbal message contained in the Pocari Sweat: Sweat For Dream advertisement can be seen below.

Table 1. Discussion of Analysis Based on Verbal Signs

No	Narrative	Say	Connotative Meaning/Denotative Meaning	Information
1.	While chasing your dreams you may feel lonely.	Chase	Connotative meaning	Hard work to achieve a goal Ambition
		Dream	Connotative meaning	
2.	But don't give up, you are not alone.		Denotative meaning	
3.	Move forward together step by step.	Advanced	Connotative meaning	Develop Stages/process to achieve a goal.
		Step by step.	Connotative meaning	
4.	Enjoy a trip full of smiles and memories.	Journey	Connotative meaning	The process/moment that is passed in an effort to achieve a goal. Happiness/joy.
		Smile	Connotative meaning	
5.	Even though we are different, our spirit remains the same.	Different	Connotative meaning	Have different desires/goals/aspirations.
6.	Don't give up on your dreams.	Dream	Connotative meaning	Ambition
7.	Because there will be friends with you, believe me tomorrow will be brighter.	Tomorrow	Connotative meaning	The future / Future time. Good / Happy.
		Sunny	Connotative meaning	

Source: Researcher's Process (2021)

Apart from being formed by spoken verbal messages, the Pocari Sweat advertisement: Sweat For Dream also formed by written verbal messages. In contrast to the spoken verbal message which is in the form of quite long sentences, the written verbal message is in the form of words/sentences, the slogan and theme of this Pocari Sweat advertisement. More clearly, some of the words/sentences that make up the written verbal message are as follows:

- Sweat For Dream
- Go Sweat Go Ion

The first sentence is "Sweat For Dream", the sentence which is the theme of this Pocari Sweat advertisement. If interpreted in Indonesian, namely sweat for Mimi, the meaning of this sentence actually means that we have to try and fight to achieve what we dream of, we cannot just stay silent to achieve our dreams. Because, to achieve what we dream of, there must always be struggles and sacrifices that we have to make and go through.

Then in the sentence "Go Sweat Go Ion", which is the tagline sentence for the Pocari Sweat product, has the meaning of an invitation to move actively, sweat, and carry out activities such as exercising and other useful activities to maintain a healthy body. And invites you to consume Pocari Sweat, which is able to restore body ions after activity.

Non Verbal

Non-verbal communication is communication whose message is packaged in non-verbal form, without words. Non-verbal communication in the form of any information or emotion communicated without using words or non-linguistics. Nonverbal communication is important in communication because what we often do has a much more important meaning than what we say (Budyatna 2011:110). Cangara (in Fadillah Mursyid Ritonga, 2017:75) divides non-verbal codes into 12 forms, but here the author only uses 6 forms of non-verbal communication to explain the non-verbal meaning contained in this research. The six forms of non-verbal communication are: kinesics, eye movements, paralanguage, proximity, artifacts & visualization, and color.

Table 2. Discussion of Analysis Based on Non-Verbal Signs

No	Type	Form	Meaning
1.	<i>Kinesic</i>	The movement of the head lowers, then looks up.	the return of hope, optimism, confidence and enthusiasm within oneself.
		Facial expressions with wide open eyes and smiles, accompanied by energetic body movements.	very high enthusiasm or passionate enthusiasm for practicing to achieve a dream.
		Running movements along with a cheerful expression.	support each other and encourage each other.
		The movement of taking a bottle of Pocari Sweat, then drinking it.	Invitation to consume Pocari Sweat.
		Sitting quietly pensive with a gloomy expression and a blank stare.	Do not get excited
2.	Eye Movement	The movement of the eyes looking down, and then looking up.	Return of confidence and enthusiasm.
3.	<i>Paralanguae</i>	The intonation pressure rises and the voice is loud.	Enthusiasm and optimism
4.	<i>Proximity</i>	Personal distance	Close friend.
5.	<i>Artifacts and Visual</i>	Different clothes and attributes.	Different hobbies/abilities and dreams/aspirations.
		High school clothes	High school teenager.
6.	Color	Shades of black	Silence/Silence.
		Shades of orange and yellow.	Excitement, cheerfulness, happiness, determination and energy.
		Shades of blue.	Confidence and freshness.

Source: Researcher's Process (2021)

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

There are several conclusions from the results of research conducted by researchers, including: Pocari Sweat advertisement: Sweat For Dream with the theme of the spirit of achieving dreams. This means that the process of achieving a dream is not easy, there will always be obstacles and hurdles that must be overcome. However, don't let all that stop you from achieving your dreams. We must be able to rise and always believe that we will definitely be able to achieve our dreams. Passionately through all the processes we have gone through and will go through in achieving the dreams we want.

Based on Ferdinand De Saussure's semiotic analysis, the Pocari Sweat advertisement: Sweat For Dream These are classified based on signs, markers and

omens. Firstly, in terms of signs, what is dominant in this advertisement is the sign message shown through visual illustrations of high school teenage characters in achieving their dreams, which tell about complaints and enthusiasm in achieving dreams. Second, in terms of markers, what is dominant in this advertisement are expressions, body movements and color nuances. And thirdly, in a sign, what is dominant in this advertisement is the enthusiasm and struggle in achieving dreams.

In Symbolic Interaction Analysis, which is classified based on verbal and non-verbal symbols. The dominant verbal message in this advertisement is conveyed through narration spoken by male and female narrators. The essence of the narration tells about the complaints experienced by almost everyone in achieving their dreams, which then in the narration gives encouragement to everyone not to give up easily. dreams, and must remain optimistic and full of enthusiasm to achieve dreams. And the non-verbal messages in this advertisement are displayed through kinesics, eye movements, paralangue, proximity, artifacts and visuals, and colors which are very appropriate and supportive in conveying the content of the message in the advertisement.

FURTHER STUDY

Based on the results of the research that has been carried out, there are several suggestions that the author will convey, including:

Pocari Sweat advertisement: Sweat For Dream This is very good, which has a message to encourage you not to give up easily in achieving your dreams, which is packaged through good visual illustrations and narration. However, perhaps you should pay more attention to the pronunciation of the narrative in advertisements delivered by the narrator, because it sounds like a normal person speaking. It should be possible to adapt more closely to the content of the sentences conveyed, so that the impression and message you want to convey in this advertisement can be better conveyed to the audience.

For readers of the results of this research, especially those with an interest in semiotics, Ferdinand De Saussure, and advertising, the results of this research can be additional knowledge and reference for users and readers of this research.

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